

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF GREEN INVESTMENT PROJECTS TO INCREASE THE DEMAND FOR INTERNATIONAL FOOD PRODUCTS IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. *The article in question develops proposals aimed at increasing the volume of fruit and vegetable products to meet the population's demand for food. International economic relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, green investment projects, and the problem of food security are revealed.*

Keywords: *food security, sustainable development, innovative activity, innovative approach, green investment projects, import, export.*

Introduction

One of the main goals of the reforms carried out in our country in recent years has been to meet the population's demand for food by ensuring sustainable economic growth, increase the level of food security development, and increase the role of food products in the well-being of the population.

As you know, today the issue of food security remains one of the global problems that worries the whole world. According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), currently, almost 30 percent of the world's population suffers from malnutrition.

Under such conditions, large-scale work has been carried out in our republic in recent years to ensure a stable supply of high-quality and sufficient food products to the population.

The situation with the production and processing of food products remains difficult and largely depends on imports and state support for agriculture. All this affects the quality and safety of raw materials and products.

“***We do not eat to live, but live to eat.***” This aphorism is known to many, but sooner or later we all face it in our lives. True, often it happens the other way around, and food is the only thing that brings pleasure and allows you to relax. Of course, food is essential for all organisms, it's hard to argue with that. It serves as a source of energy, as well as a building material for cells. But the place of man in preserving the naturalness of the gifts of nature, which are the source of food products on Earth, is unique.

Agriculture is one of the promising sources of strengthening the country's export potential, along with meeting the needs of the population of our state for food products, and the processing industry sectors for high-quality raw materials.

Much attention is paid to the consistent development of the agro-industrial complex and its locomotive, that is, diversified farms, which are its driving force, in order to reform agriculture and ensure food security; along with supporting the farming movement in the agrarian sector, work is being carried out consistently to gradually transfer cotton and grain growing to a cluster form.

In the agricultural production of our republic, comprehensive measures are being implemented to reduce labor and energy costs, save resources, use advanced “green” technologies for chemical treatment of crops, produce high-quality agricultural products, and create high-performance agricultural machinery. Particular attention is paid to the development of technical

means that ensure high-quality implementation of all technological processes with low labor costs and resource consumption, satisfying the demand for food products through green investment projects.

The Strategy for Actions on Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, including “...more than doubling the gross domestic product by 2030, optimizing the sown food area for 2017-2020, rational use of land and water resources, implementation of modern green intensive agricultural technologies, consistent development of agricultural production and expansion of environmentally friendly products” sets tasks.

This article serves to a certain extent to implement the tasks defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 “On the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021”, Resolution № PQ-3117 dated July 7, 2017 “On measures for the further development of the scientific and technical base in the agricultural engineering sector”, and other normative and legal documents related to this activity.

Discussion and results of the study.

In order to effectively implement reforms and eliminate existing shortcomings in the electricity and oil and gas industries that hinder innovative development, as well as provide our people with constant access to important resources, the Ministry of Energy was created in 2019. On August 22, 2019, our President signed a decree “On urgent measures to improve the energy efficiency of economic and social sectors, the introduction of energy-saving technologies and the development of renewable energy sources.” The main goal is to increase energy efficiency, widespread introduction of energy-saving green technologies and renewable energy sources, taking into account the best foreign experience, a sharp reduction in energy consumption in economic sectors and the social sphere, ensuring rational and efficient use of resources.

In our republic, it is necessary to focus on the rapid development of all sectors of agriculture, including fruits, grapes and melons, increasing soil fertility, increasing their productivity, improving product quality and storing them during the off-season in order to fully meet the demand of our people for fruits and grapes.

Table 1

Indicators of fruit and vegetable production by region in 2021¹

¹ Information of the Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Bringing the development of the agricultural sector to a new stage corresponds only to the goal of directly introducing innovations into agricultural production.

Andijan (23.0%), Fergana (13.0%), Samarkand (12.6%), Namangan (10.4%) and Bukhara (9.2%) regions accounted for the largest share of the total volume of fruits and vegetables grown by region in 2021. At the same time, the lowest share in the total volume of fruits and vegetables was observed in Syrdarya region (1.5%) and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (2.2%).

High growth rates during the indicated periods were recorded in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (106.9%), Syrdarya (105.7%), Kashkadarya (105.6%), Surkhandarya (104.9%), and Namangan (104.8%) regions.

Based on the above information, it should be emphasized that increasing the efficiency and ensuring the sustainability of our country's agriculture is directly related to the development of green technologies in the production of agricultural products, the use of modern agricultural machinery, the development of processing industries, improving the use of land and other types of resources, eliminating the disproportionality in the assessment of industrial and agricultural products, implementing a set of measures by the state to support rural areas, developing production and social infrastructure, improving domestic economic relations, improving the quality of services, and using modern scientifically justified methods in the management of this sector.

During the implementation of the above tasks, in 2021, the volume of products (services) of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in our country amounted to 104.0% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year (January-December 2020 compared to January-December 2019 - 102.9%), including in agriculture and animal husbandry, hunting and services provided in these sectors - 103.9% (102.9%), forestry - 101.5% (101.7%), fishing - 121.4% (117.9%).

We believe that it is important to add social aspects to the concept of “food security” enshrined in the Rome Declaration on World Food Security, based on such important elements as physical (quantitative) and economic access to food, food independence, reliability and stability. Food security is ensured at various levels. Therefore, it manifests itself in various forms. In our opinion, it is advisable to interpret the levels of food security as follows.

A high level of food security - when the production of agricultural products and foodstuffs exceeds the minimum necessary level of consumption by the population, is provided only by domestic producers and is exported;

Ensured food security - when the production of agricultural products and foodstuffs basically meets the internal needs of the state and consumption is higher than the necessary minimum level of the population, provided by domestic producers;

Additionally provided food security - when the production of agricultural products and foodstuffs does not fully satisfy the internal needs of the state, some food products are imported from foreign countries in order for consumption to exceed the necessary minimum level;

Food dependence - when the production of agricultural products and foodstuffs does not meet the internal needs of the state, the necessary minimum level of consumption is ensured on the basis of import of food products from foreign (third) countries.

External threats to national food security are manifested in socio-economic and political processes, factors and realities that arise and pose a threat to it outside the country, including on a global and global scale, as well as in neighboring and partner countries.

Is considered the most acceptable international standard in the intensive development of the agricultural sector of our republic, in the production of high-quality and safe agricultural and

food products. Also, brief information is given on the procedure for implementing the GLOBAL GAP standard, the 3 basic modules, and the procedure and requirements for certification.

The convenience of this standard today provides an opportunity to produce and prepare agricultural and food products based on the requirements of not only domestic but also international markets. Products grown on the basis of the requirements of this standard contribute to consumers, producers, and the country's economic development. Lack of testing centers and laboratories that meet international requirements, the absence of a certification body for the GLOBAL G.A.P. standard, lack of qualified specialists, etc.

In order to further improve the quality and safety of agricultural products, increase their competitiveness and develop export opportunities, taking into account existing difficulties, it is advisable to implement the proposed action plan.

Table 2

The growth dynamics of enterprises with a GLOBAL G.A.P. certificate worldwide².

Uzbekistan's reforms in the food sector are also widely recognized by the international community.

According to the data, there is so much food in Uzbekistan that each citizen can consume 39 kilocalories per day. Data from international organizations and national institutes were used in the calculations. The country's high position in the ranking indicates a high level of its food security.

Today, food manufacturing enterprises are faced with the task of improving the quality of production and introducing new standards for its management, and modern technologies. Their implementation will allow in the future to raise the capacities of enterprises to a new level, improve the quality of manufactured products, and expand their range. In addition, the preparation of enterprises for certification according to the new rules, retraining of personnel, creation of special repair teams and other issues are of great importance.

According to the information service of the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, The volume of exports of fruits and vegetables and their processed products amounted to 708.8 million US dollars, or increased by 15.6 percent compared to the same period last year.

In the total volume of fruits and vegetables and their processed products, the share of fruits and melons is 35.9 percent (an increase of 17.0 percent compared to the same period last year), vegetables 30.7 percent (an increase of 18.6 percent), grapes 22, 5 percent (increased by 12.2 percent), processed fruit and vegetable products - 4.1 percent (increased by 49.9 percent).

² "Standard" G.A.P. - Good Agricultural Practices

The main foreign trade partners are Kazakhstan (46.7% in total), Russia (18.0%), Afghanistan (6.6%), China (5.7%), Turkey (4.5%), Kyrgyzstan (4.3%) and Iraq (1, 7%).

Conclusion

The implementation of these measures at the current stage of reforms carried out in our country will allow, by ensuring long-term sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing, increasing the efficiency of the sector, to meet the demand for food products, ensure its safety, expand the export geography and improve the living conditions of our people.

Green economy investments are critical to achieving sustainable and inclusive growth.

The research carried out shows that the import of food products makes it possible to increase the level of food security in the domestic market, reduce prices and create a competitive environment for local producers, which, as a result, forces them to increase efficiency. Export of food products provides local producers the opportunity to compete in foreign markets and, at the same time, forces them to reduce costs and operate more efficiently.

REFERENCES

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. 29.12.2020 // "Khalk sozi" newspaper, December 30, 2020, No. 276 (7778).
2. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers on the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017 (January 14, 2017).
3. "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022
4. Uzbekistan Republic Employment and work relations ministry and "Roadmap" on improving and increasing the efficiency of work on ensuring employment of the population, developed by the Ministry of Finance . <https://www.norma.uz>
5. Bekmurodov A. Sh ., Gafurov He . V. _ Uzbekistan the economy modernization and reforms of deepening new and high stage on the way - T .: Economy , 2008. – 126 p .
6. Shoimardonkulovich, Y.D (2020). The importance of management in the field of service. Voprosy science and education, (14 (98)), 16-19.
7. Burkhanov, S.N (2022). Development of "green economy" in the sectors of the economy and its prospects. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(5), 1332–1337
8. O. Khamidov. D. Sh. Yavmutov and SN Burkhanov Problems of the effective use of irrigated land in Bukhara region and ways to improve them. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202343101056>
9. <https://stat.uz>